

Personalized striatal targets for deep brain stimulation in obsessive-compulsive disorder

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Running Title

Personalized OCD striatal DBS targets

1 ABSTRACT

2

3 Background: Psychiatric conditions currently treated with deep brain stimulation
4 (DBS), such as obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD), are heterogeneous diseases with
5 different symptomatic dimensions, indicating that fixed neuroanatomical DBS targets
6 for all OCD cases may not be efficacious.

7 Objective/Hypothesis: We tested whether the optimal DBS target for OCD is fixed for
8 all patients or whether it is individualized and related to each patient's symptomatic
9 content. Further, we explored if the optimal target can be predicted by combining
10 functional neuroimaging and structural connectivity.

11 Methods: In a prospective, randomized, double-blinded study in 7 OCD patients,
12 symptomatic content was characterized pre-operatively by clinical interview and OCD
13 symptom-provocation during functional MRI. DBS electrode implantation followed a
14 trajectory placing 4 contacts along a striatal axis (nucleus accumbens to caudate).
15 Patients underwent three-month stimulation periods for each contact (and sham),
16 followed by clinical evaluation. Probabilistic tractography, applied to diffusion-
17 weighted images acquired pre-operatively, was used to study the overlap between
18 projections from the prefrontal areas activated during symptom provocation and the
19 volume of activated tissue of each electrode contact.

20 Results: Six patients were classified responders, with median symptomatic reduction
21 of 50% achieved from each patient's best contact. This was located at the caudate in 4
22 cases and at the accumbens in 2. Critically, the anatomical locus of the best contact
23 (accumbens or caudate) was related to an index derived by combining functional MRI
24 responses to prevailing symptom provocation and prefronto-cortico-striatal projections
25 defined by probabilistic tractography.

26 Conclusion: Our results therefore represent a step towards personalized, content-
27 specific DBS targets for OCD.

28

29 **Key words: deep brain stimulation, striatum, obsessive-compulsive disorder,**
30 **functional MRI, probabilistic tractography**

31 INTRODUCTION

32 Following the success of deep brain stimulation (DBS) in treating certain neurological
33 conditions such as Parkinson's disease and essential tremor, DBS is being increasingly
34 used in the management of psychiatric disorders, including treatment-resistant
35 obsessive- compulsive disorder (OCD) [1–4]. OCD is characterized by intrusive
36 distressing thoughts (obsessions) and/or repetitive mental or behavioral acts
37 (compulsions) and is a leading cause of illness- related disability [5,6]. DBS for OCD
38 has targeted regions considered components of the reward and motivation system, such
39 as the nucleus accumbens (NAcc) [7], the ventral capsule/ventral striatum VC/VS [8]
40 and the limbic portion of the subthalamic nucleus (STN) [9], as well as the anterior limb
41 of the internal capsule (ALIC) [10] and the inferior thalamic peduncle (ITP) [11]. One
42 fundamental limitation, however, is that, in contrast to neurological conditions such as
43 essential tremor where the symptomatology is relatively fixed across patients,
44 psychiatric symptoms show heterogeneity in terms of their content. In treatment-
45 resistant OCD patients undergoing DBS this is particularly relevant. OCD is a
46 heterogeneous disease in which different behaviors, or symptomatic dimensions, are
47 expressed [12]. Patients may show obsessions or compulsions of contamination and
48 washing, forbidden thoughts, doubts and checking, symmetry and ordering, repeating or
49 hoarding [13]. Seventy-four percent of patients are reported to fit into this classification
50 [14], and some patients express a combination of symptom dimensions. Despite this
51 heterogeneity, current DBS approaches target the same site across patients, regardless of
52 the content of their symptoms.

53 Determining the predominant symptoms in a given patient relies on clinical evaluation.
54 The characterization of the neural substrates of different symptomatic dimensions in
55 OCD has employed functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), applied in the
56 context of presenting patients with images corresponding to specific symptom
57 dimensions using the Maudsley Obsessive-Compulsive Stimuli Set (MOCSS) [15]. This
58 symptom provocation method reveals activations in different areas of the prefrontal
59 cortex, selectively for each symptomatic dimension. For example, patients with
60 contamination obsessions mainly activate the medial orbitofrontal (ventromedial)
61 cortex, while those who present checking symptoms chiefly activate the dorsolateral
62 prefrontal cortex (PFC) [15]. These different areas of the prefrontal cortex project to the

63 striatum into different ventrodorsally distributed areas, and not only to the NAcc or
64 ventral striatum (VS). For example, ventromedial and orbitofrontal cortex project to
65 NAcc, but dorsal anterior cingulate and dorsolateral PFC project to more dorsal portions
66 of the striatum [16–18]. Given that the pathophysiology of obsessive-compulsive
67 disorder (OCD) is thought to involve abnormal activity in fronto-striatal circuits
68 [19,20], differential engagement of PFC subdivisions during the MOCSS task as a
69 function of symptom dimension is important because it implies that different
70 subdivisions of the striatum may be differentially implicated in a given OCD patient's
71 pathophysiology. Thus, if during symptom provocation a patient exhibits increased
72 activity in dorsal frontal areas, which form part of fronto-striatal circuits involving
73 striatal regions dorsal to the NAcc, it is possible that this patient will not improve with
74 NAcc or VS stimulation simply because DBS has not targeted the pathological circuit.

75 Recent studies on DBS in OCD have shown that the overall control achieved by
76 stimulating different targets (the same single target being used in all patients within
77 each cohort) is about 50% of clinical responders [21,22]. This contrasts with patients
78 with essential tremor, in whom thalamic DBS produces postural tremor reduction in
79 89% of cases [23]. We considered that the explanation for the 50% clinical response
80 rate is the approach of treating all OCD cases with a single target, independently of their
81 symptom content. We hypothesized that the optimal striatal target for DBS in OCD
82 patients is located along the dorsoventral axis of the striatum – not limited to the NAcc
83 (or VS) – depending on the dysfunctional fronto-striatal circuit. This, in turn, would
84 depend on the particular symptom dimension of each patient, with predominant
85 symptom(s) defined as the most severe, resistant to treatment and disabling OCD
86 symptoms at the time of recruitment. To test this hypothesis, we characterized symptom
87 content-specificity of individual OCD patients using symptom-provocation fMRI prior
88 to DBS implantation. Subsequently, in a prospective double-blinded study in a series of
89 7 OCD patients that were candidates for psychiatric surgery, we tested the clinical
90 efficacy of different electrode contacts distributed along the striatum, spanning the
91 caudate and NAcc (**Figure 1**). This comprised three months of bilateral stimulation (4.5
92 V stimulation at a frequency of 130 Hz and pulse-width 60 μ s) in every electrode
93 contact (0, 1, 2, 3) and sham period (no stimulation). Furthermore, we present a novel
94 method to determine, *a priori*, which stimulation site would be optimal. Patients
95 underwent pre-operative diffusion-weighted MRI imaging (DWI) and projections

96 between prefrontal activations during symptom provocation and the 4 contact points
97 along the striatal axis were determined by applying probabilistic tractography to these
98 images. For each stimulated site, the density of prefronto-striatal projections was
99 subsequently compared with clinical efficacy of stimulation.

100

101 **METHODS**

102 *Patients*

103 Seven patients, three male aged 21-50 years; average 36.67, and four female aged 28-46
104 years; average 35.25, suffering from treatment-refractory obsessive-compulsive disorder
105 participated in this study. All patients scored 24 or higher in the Yale-Brown Obsessive-
106 Compulsive Scale (Y-BOCS) [24]. All patients provided written informed consent. The
107 study had approval from the Hospital Clínico San Carlos Ethics Committee. The study
108 is registered at clinicaltrials.gov under trial name “Deep brain Stimulation in Obsessive-
109 compulsive Disorder: Randomized, Double-blinded Clinical Trial (10/131)”,
110 registration number: NCT03217123.

111 *Patient inclusion*

112 Between June 2011 and December 2014, all patients diagnosed with OCD who attended
113 the outpatient clinic at the Psychiatry Department of Hospital Clínico San Carlos
114 (Madrid, Spain) and met study inclusion criteria were invited to participate in this study.
115 Patient demographic details are provided in **Table S1**. Inclusion criteria for functional
116 neurosurgical management were a) age 18-50 years; b) severe chronic form of
117 treatment-resistant OCD according to DSM-IV Revised criteria; c) duration of illness
118 of at least 5 years without remission; d) a Y-BOCS score $\geq 24/40$; e) treatments with
119 maximum tolerated dose of at least five serotonin reuptake inhibitors for at least 10
120 weeks, treatment with clomipramine, buspirone and lithium for at least 4 weeks, as
121 well as psychotherapy (a minimum of 20 sessions of therapist-guided exposure and
122 response prevention) simultaneously with pharmacotherapy; f) no changes in prescribed
123 medication for at least 4 weeks before; g) inability to carry out a normal social/family
124 life and impairment in daily life function; h) availability of protective and supportive
125 legal, social and familial environment for surgical treatment and rehabilitation periods;
126 i) consensus that the patient is a candidate for DBS for OCD by two independent 5

127 psychiatrists, with approval from an independent psychiatric surgery committee
128 composed of one neurosurgeon, one psychiatrist and one legal medicine expert; j)
129 ability to provide written consent for the study.

130 Exclusion criteria were: a) past or present diagnosis of psychotic disorder; b) present or
131 past substance abuse; c) any current clinically significant neurological disorder or
132 medical illness; d) any clinically significant abnormality on preoperative magnetic
133 resonance imaging; e) any DBS contraindication.

134 All patients were blind to stimulation protocol throughout the study.

135 *Psychiatric assessment*

136 Y-BOCS was the primary psychiatric variable for this study. Predominant obsessions
137 and compulsions for each patient were recorded at baseline according to standardized
138 evaluation using Y-BOCS total score. Additionally, clinical change was measured by
139 the Global Assessment of Function (GAF) score [25] and the Clinical Global
140 Impression (CGI) [26]. Thus, patients were clinically assessed with Y-BOCS, GAF and
141 CGI at baseline, at the end of every trial – three months of stimulation in every contact:
142 0, 1, 2, 3 and sham period – and after each one-month wash-out period. Standardized
143 clinical evaluation was done by a psychiatrist who was blind to stimulation protocol.
144 Pharmacological treatment did not change during the study period in all cases with the
145 exception of small variations in benzodiazepine dosage. Psychiatric scores along all
146 trials are provided in **Table S2**.

147 *Neuropsychological assessment*

148 Neuropsychological evaluation was conducted following each psychiatric assessment,
149 with evaluator blind to stimulation protocol. The main cognitive domains were
150 assessed: Free Cued Serial Recall Test [27] in abbreviated form (only 2 of the 3 test
151 trials) for learning and memory (3 different versions of the task were used across the
152 longitudinal study); Stroop Color-Word Interference Test [28] for cognitive control and
153 inhibition; phonological verbal fluency [29] and categorical verbal fluency [30] for
154 verbal fluency [31]; Letter-number sequencing from WAIS-IV for Working memory
155 [32]; Trail Making test subtest A (TMT-A) and subtest B (TMT-B) [33] for sustained
156 and divided attention, and the Wisconsin Card Sorting Test [34] for set-shifting
157 abilities, among executive functions. Neuropsychology scores at baseline, contact zero 6

158 and best contact are provided in **Table S3**.

159 *Pre-surgical Structural Neuroimaging*

160 Before surgery, structural and functional data were acquired for all patients on a 3T
161 Siemens TRIO system (Siemens, Erlangen, Germany). A standard 8 channel head coil
162 was used to acquire MPRAGE T1-weighted anatomical images with 1mm³ resolution
163 [repetition time (TR), 2300 ms; echo time (TE), 2.98 ms; flip angle, 9°] and diffusion-
164 weighted images (DWI). DWI acquisition was based on parameters used in previous
165 probabilistic tractography studies of the basal ganglia [34]. Each volume consisted of 40
166 axial slices of 2.3mm thickness with no interslice gaps and an acquisition matrix of 96 x
167 96 in a field of view (FoV) of 220 x 100 mm, resulting in 2.3 x 2.3 x 2.3 mm³ isotropic
168 voxels [TR, 5800 ms; TE, 103 ms; flip angle, 90°; bandwidth, 2004 Hz/pixel]. In order
169 to increase signal-to-noise, we acquired two contiguous sequences of 128 diffusion-
170 weighted images. Each dataset consisted of 64 images with diffusion gradients applied
171 along 64 non-collinear encoding directions for two different diffusion sensitization
172 strengths ($b = 500, 100\text{s/mm}^2$), and one additional image with no diffusion weighting
173 ($b = 0\text{ s/mm}^2$). A b value of zero delivers a T2-weighted EPI image for anatomical
174 reference.

175 *Pre-surgical Functional Neuroimaging*

176 fMRI data acquisition

177 For each patient, 625 gradient-echo echo-planar T2*-weighted MR image volumes with
178 blood oxygenation level-dependent (BOLD) contrast were acquired during symptom
179 provocation, plus five additional volumes, acquired at the start of each session and
180 subsequently discarded, to allow for T1 equilibration effects. Each whole-brain volume
181 comprised 40 axial slices (2.2mm thick; distance factor 0.25; TR 2.43 s; TE 30 ms; flip
182 angle 90°) sequentially acquired (ascending).

183 Symptom-provocation fMRI experiment

184 In the context of fMRI scanning, all patients performed an OCD symptom provocation
185 task. We employed a modified version of the OCD symptom-provocation paradigm
186 using the Maudsley Obsessive–Compulsive Stimuli Set (MOCSS) developed by
187 Mataix-Cols [15,35]. During scanning, patients were presented with pictures of 4
188 classes of provocative stimuli, 50 of each type: 1) contamination/washing, 2) checking, 7

189 3) hoarding, 4) symmetry/order [15,35]. Examples of washing-related pictures included
190 a public toilet, money, and a syringe. Examples of checking-related pictures included
191 electric appliances (computer, kettle, light switch), an open door, and a purse. Examples
192 of hoarding-related scenes included old newspapers/magazines, old clothes/toys, empty
193 bottles/cans, and trash bins. Examples of symmetry-related scenes included books in a
194 bookcase, a CD rack and a bathroom cabinet. In addition, 50 pictures of neutral scenes
195 (e.g., furniture, nature scenes household items) were selected from a standard set of
196 stimuli [36]. These stimuli had previously been carefully chosen [35] to avoid
197 resembling common triggers of OCD symptoms. Note that 11 pictures of the MOCSS,
198 pertaining to UK electrical plugs/sockets, money, cash-point and written English, were
199 substituted for equivalent Spanish pictures obtained with a standard digital camera
200 (Sony NEX-VG10E).

201 The study comprised 4 ‘blocks’ pertaining to the 4 classes of provocative stimuli. Each
202 block consisted of ten 20s alternating epochs in which subjects viewed either 10
203 provocative or 10 neutral pictures. Each picture was presented for 1950 ms (inter-
204 stimulus interval 50 ms). Each epoch began with an 8 s period during which patients
205 were played a prerecorded voice via MR-compatible headphones (VisuaStim XGA;
206 Resonance Technology, Northridge, CA), instructing them to imagine being in a
207 particular situation while looking at the scenes they were about to see (there were five
208 slightly different recordings per type of stimuli in each experiment, to avoid monotony).
209 We presented the same instructions as used previously [15], but recorded in Spanish.
210 Some examples of these instructions are the following: For washing-related pictures:
211 “Imagine that you must come into contact with what’s shown in the following pictures
212 without washing yourself afterward.” For checking-related pictures: “Imagine that you
213 are not sure whether you switched off or locked the following objects and it is
214 impossible for you to go back and check.” For hoarding-related pictures: “Imagine that
215 the following objects belong to you and that you must throw them away forever.” For
216 symmetry-related pictures: “Imagine that you are not allowed to put the following items
217 in order.” For neutral scenes: “Imagine that you are completely relaxed while looking at
218 the following scenes.” After each set of pictures, another prerecorded sound file of the
219 question “How anxious do you feel?” was played. Patients had to rate their subjective
220 anxiety by pushing one of 5 buttons to indicate from 0 (no anxiety) to 4 (extreme
221 anxiety).

222 *Neurosurgical procedure*

223 The day before the operation, a volumetric CT scan (Philips ® Brilliance 64 CT
224 Scanner) was performed and fused with a contrast-enhanced T1 MRI and T2 volumetric
225 images. The location of the posterior border of the anterior commissure (AC) and the
226 anterior border of the posterior commissure (PC) were marked, and the target
227 determined by measuring the distances from the AC-PC line and the mid-sagittal plane,
228 using a Medtronic Stealth Station Treon navigation system (Medtronic Minneapolis,
229 USA). The target for the NAcc was placed at the coordinates reported by [7]: 2.5 mm
230 rostral to the anterior border of the anterior commissure, 4.5 mm ventral to the AC-PC
231 line, and 6.5 mm lateral to the mid- sagittal plane. A trajectory was planned to reach the
232 target point at the NAcc close to the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis (distal electrode
233 or contact “0”), and for placing the rest of the contacts of a Medtronic Model 3391
234 stimulating macroelectrode at several points along the striatum avoiding the ventricles
235 (contacts 1, 2, and 3; **Figure 1 and Figure S1**).

236 On the operative day, a burr hole was performed on each side, the dura opened and the
237 hole sealed with DuraSeal (DuraSeal Dural Sealant System, Confluent Surgical, Inc.,
238 Waltham, Massachusetts) to avoid CSF reflux. A microelectrode FC 4000 (FHC,
239 Bowdoin, Maine, USA) was advanced into the ventral striatum towards the target using
240 a Microdrive (Elekta MicroDrive™). In the case of relatively silent neuronal activity,
241 the target was advanced 2 mm anteriorly. After microelectrode recording, the
242 macroelectrode was implanted at the determined target, and the clinical effects were
243 tested using an external tester (Medtronic Model 3625 Test Stimulator). Bipolar
244 stimulation at 3.5 V between the most distal and the most proximal contacts (negative
245 polarity most distal) was delivered at 130 Hz (pulse width 60 µs), and then increased up
246 to 5 V to screen for undesired side effects (none of which appeared in any case). Intra-
247 operative X-ray was used to verify the positioning of the two electrodes. Post-operative
248 CT verified final electrode position.

249 After implantation, the lead extensions were externalized and all possible combinations
250 of the electrode leads were tested for their effectiveness using an external tester. After
251 the external stimulation trial period, an Activa PC Model 37601 neurostimulator
252 (Medtronic Inc) was implanted subcutaneously at the abdominal left flank and
253 connected to the electrodes using an extension cable 33086 (Medtronic Inc).

254 *Deep brain Stimulation Protocol*

255 After surgery, a simple randomized sequence of contact activations (C0, 1, 2, 3) and
256 sham (-), was generated for each patient. Each contact was stimulated at 130 Hz, pulse-
257 width 60 μ s, and 4.5 V for three months (the sham activation was 0 V) according to the
258 patient's individual sequence, separated by one month of washout with the generator
259 turned off (**Figure 1**). The study meets a double-blind, longitudinal design. Stimulation
260 contact was set following a random series known only by the neurosurgeon, whereas
261 patient, psychiatry and neuropsychology teams were blinded. Some patients referred a
262 transient sense of wellbeing when contact 0 was stimulated for the first time during
263 stimulation trials prior to, but not during, the longitudinal study.

264 **Statistical analysis**

265 *Statistical Analysis of Psychiatric and Neuropsychological Data*

266 Psychiatric and neuropsychological scale results in the multiple stimulation periods
267 were analyzed with repeated measures non-parametric Friedman test. To evaluate
268 pairwise significant differences between the pre-surgery scores, C0 score, and BC
269 scores, non-parametric Wilcoxon's test was used. All statistical analyses were
270 performed using IBM SPSS Statistics software version 20, and results considered
271 significant at alpha level 0.05. Statistical parameters can be found in the Results section.

272 *Neuroimaging analysis*

273 **fMRI Data Analysis**

274 Functional imaging data were analyzed using statistical parametric mapping (SPM12;
275 <http://www.fil.ion.ucl.ac.uk/spm>) employing an epoch-related model. Each imaging
276 time series was realigned to correct for interscan movement, slice-time corrected,
277 normalized into a standard anatomical space, and smoothed with a Gaussian kernel of
278 8mm full width half-maximum. To test for symptom-provocation effects, we specified
279 four effects of interest: the epochs corresponding to each symptom dimension. Epoch-
280 specific responses were modeled by convolving a box-car function spanning epoch
281 duration with a canonical hemodynamic response function (HRF) to create regressors of
282 interest. Events corresponding to viewing instructions, and questions regarding anxiety
283 levels, were modeled as separate regressors. Six movement parameters were modeled as
284 nuisance covariates.

285 The predominant symptom(s) for each patient was defined (**Table 1**) and used to
286 construct a contrast of responses to provocation relative to the neutral pictures baseline.
287 The ensuing statistical parametric map for this contrast was thresholded at $P < 0.001$
288 uncorrected (unless otherwise stated). Note that due to weak responses during symptom
289 activation in patients 4 and 6, the SPMs for these patients were first thresholded at $P <$
290 0.01 and 0.005 uncorrected, respectively. AlphaSim was used to correct for multiple
291 comparisons at the cluster level ($P < 0.05$) for each patient. Alphasim thresholding was
292 performed for the number of comparisons defined within a prefrontal mask accounting
293 for the applied smoothing, (FWHM 8mm). Different cluster thresholds (K) were
294 obtained for the three pre-defined statistical thresholds: $P < 0.01$ $K > 86$; $P < 0.005$ $K > 58$;
295 $P < 0.001$ $K > 26$. The prefrontal mask was created by combining the following regions
296 from the Harvard-Oxford cortical atlas distributed with FSL
297 (<https://fsl.fmrib.ox.ac.uk/fsl/fslwiki>): Superior Frontal Gyrus, Middle Frontal Gyrus,
298 Inferior Frontal Gyrus pars triangularis and pars opercularis, Frontal Orbital Cortex,
299 Supplementary motor cortex, Paracingulate Gyrus, Frontal Pole, Cingulate Gyrus
300 (Anterior Division), Subcallosal Cortex, Frontal Operculum Cortex, and Frontal Medial
301 Cortex.

302 Probabilistic Tractography Analysis

303 In a first step, each patient's electrode contacts were localized as follows. We extracted
304 subject-specific volumetric masks of the caudate and accumbens nucleus in both
305 hemispheres using an automated sub-cortical segmentation procedure in Freesurfer
306 V5.1.0 [36]. Affine linear transformations between different image spaces were
307 performed using FSL FLIRT [37]. Non-brain tissues were removed from T1-weighted
308 images using FSL BET [38]. Post-operative CT images were thresholded to segment the
309 skull and remove it from the unthresholded image and co-registered to the pre-operative
310 T1-weighted image. The post-operative CT was again thresholded at an intensity of
311 1500 to retain just the electrodes in the T1-weighted image space. The contacts'
312 coordinates were identified visually after superimposing the post-operative CT on the
313 pre-operative T1-weighted MRI (**Figure S1**). A spherical region with a radius of 4mm
314 was then created at each contact coordinate.

315 Diffusion weighted imaging data were pre-processed using FSL BET [38] for non-brain
316 tissue removal and FSL FDT for eddy currents correction [39]. Estimation of the 11

317 diffusion parameters was performed using BEDPOSTX [40]. We used a multi-shell
318 model for the fitting of the parameters [41]. White matter connectivity was quantified
319 using probabilistic tractography with FDT Protrackx 2.0 [42]. The contact spherical
320 regions were used as seeds for the tractography analysis, and the fMRI activations were
321 used as waypoints and termination masks. The rest of the parameters for the
322 tractography analyses were kept as default, *i.e.*, 5000 streamlines per voxel, a maximum
323 length of 2000 steps, minimum step length of 0.5mm, and a curvature threshold of 80°.
324 That is, we applied the default settings in FSL, standard in the field, in our tractography
325 analyses.

326 For display of structural and functional overlap, tractographic terminations or fMRI
327 activations were projected onto a cortical mesh using CARET (Computerized
328 Anatomical Reconstruction Toolkit) software[43].

329 Pre-operative MRI index calculation

330 For a given electrode contact, or group of contacts, the MRI index, denoted as $p(\text{tracts})$,
331 is the probability (%) of reaching the fMRI activation by seeding streamlines at the
332 volume of activated tissues (VATs) of the electrode contact(s).

333

334 **RESULTS**

335 **The most effective striatal stimulation site varies between patients**

336 Electrodes were successfully placed along a striatal axis in all patients, with two
337 contacts in NAcc (C0, C1) and two in the caudate head (C2, C3), bilaterally. This is
338 evident on inspecting the fusion of each patient's post-operative computed tomography
339 (CT) scan with the pre-operative structural MRI (**Figure S1**). Across the 7 patients, the
340 main obsession(s) and compulsion(s) showed heterogeneity (**Table 1**). For each patient,
341 the contact yielding lowest Y-BOCS score achieved during the longitudinal study was
342 labeled as "best" contact (BC). The neuroanatomical locus of the BC varied between
343 patients (**Table 1, Table S2**) and was more frequently observed in caudate than
344 accumbens nucleus (**Table S3, Figure S2**). According to current convention [45],
345 patients with a Y-BOCS score decrease of more than 35% with respect to baseline are
346 considered DBS responders. Of the seven patients studied, clinical improvement
347 following BC stimulation exceeded 35% in six patients (**Table 1**), with a median (Mdn) 12

348 Y-BOCS reduction of 47.37% at their BC. Directly contrasting this finding against
 349 clinical efficacy of the commonly stimulated most distal contact (C0) in the NAcc, we
 350 observe that across the group, stimulation of C0 achieved a Mdn Y-BOCS reduction of
 351 21.62% (**Table S3**). Only two participants (28.57%) would have been classified as
 352 responders if C0 alone had been stimulated, and in both cases (Patients 1 and 3), the BC
 353 was not in contact 0 (**Table 1**), *i.e.*, stimulation at more dorsal striatal sites were more
 354 effective in these patients.

355 Differential clinical response as a function of stimulated contact was confirmed by a
 356 Friedman Test on Y-BOCS scores for all stimulation trials, baseline and sham across
 357 the 7 patients ($\chi^2(5)=17.941$, $P=0.003$, Kendall $W=0.513$). Post-hoc Wilcoxon signed-
 358 rank tests were first performed to test for improvement relative to pre-surgical baseline
 359 for all stimulated contacts and sham. Across the 7 patients, compared to pre-surgical
 360 evaluation (Mdn- Baseline_{Y-BOCS} = 32), stimulation at C0 (Mdn-C0_{Y-BOCS} = 24), C1
 361 (Mdn-C1_{Y-BOCS} = 22), C2 (Mdn-C2_{Y-BOCS} = 17), C3 (Mdn-C3_{Y-BOCS} = 22) and sham
 362 (Mdn-Sham_{Y-BOCS} = 20) stimulation all produced a significant decrease in Y-BOCS
 363 scores ($Z=-2.120$, $P=0.034$, effect size $r=0.801$; $Z=-2.371$, $P=0.018$, $r=0.896$; $Z=-$
 364 2.371 , $P=0.018$, $r=0.896$; $Z=-2.375$, $P=0.018$, $r=0.897$; $Z=-2.366$, $P=0.018$, $r=0.894$
 365 for C0, C1, C2, C3 and Sham *vs.* Baseline, respectively). Next, post-hoc Wilcoxon tests
 366 were performed on percent improvement in Y-BOCS score at BC, contact Zero and
 367 Sham (each relative to baseline). Specifically confirming our hypothesis that BC
 368 outperforms NAcc C0 stimulation, the percentage Y-BOCS score improvement was
 369 significantly greater at BC (Mdn-BC_{Y-BOCS} decrease = 47.37%) than at C0 (Mdn-C0_{Y-}
 370 _{BOCS} decrease = 21.62%) ($Z=-2.207$, $P=0.027$, $r=0.834$). There was a trend in Y-BOCS
 371 improvement at BC relative to sham stimulation (Mdn-Sham_{Y-BOCS} = 25.00%) ($Z=-$
 372 1.859 , $P=0.063$, $r=0.702$), stimulation at C0 yielded actually marginally less Y-BOCS
 373 improvement than during Sham ($Z=-1.782$, $P=0.075$, $r=0.673$). We note, however, that
 374 Patient 3 underwent a major life event during her Sham period (discussed below).
 375 Repeating the Wilcoxon test excluding this patient shows a significant improvement of
 376 BC over Sham stimulation ($Z=-1.992$, $P=0.046$, $r=0.752$) and no Y-BOCS improvement
 377 difference between C0 and Sham stimulation ($Z=-1.483$, $P=0.138$).

378 We note that in Patients 3 and 7, it is quite probable that the most distal electrode
 379 contact is placed at the ventricles (**Figure S1**). In neither case was this contact (C0) the

380 most effective contact. Y-BOCS reduction following stimulation this distal contact was
 381 either at the same level (Patient 7) or less than (Patient 3) that observed during sham
 382 stimulation.

383 In addition to our primary outcome measure (Y-BOCS), anxiety measures were
 384 collected using the STAI state scale and Hamilton anxiety rating scale (HAM-A) at all
 385 evaluation periods in Patients 4 to 7. A Friedman Test on these scores for all stimulation
 386 trials, baseline and sham across the 4 patients showed a significant effect for HAM-A
 387 ($\chi^2(5)=11.143$, $P=0.049$). Additionally, there was a trend in STAI-state improvement
 388 ($\chi^2(5)=10.857$, $P=0.054$) under the best contact relative to the rest of the trials. For both
 389 scores, post-hoc Wilcoxon tests comparing each stimulation period with baseline, or BC
 390 with baseline, did not reveal any significant effects.

391 **Striatal stimulation has limited effects on cognitive function**

392 DBS at different striatal sites produced limited effects on cognitive testing. For each
 393 neuropsychological test (**Table S4**), scores as a function of stimulated contact were
 394 entered into a Friedman Test for all stimulation trials, baseline and sham across the 7
 395 patients. Statistically significant effects were only observed for Trail Making Test-B
 396 (TMT-B) performance times ($\chi^2(5)=13.787$, $P=0.017$, Kendall $W=0.460$). Post-hoc
 397 Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were performed on scores relative to pre-surgical baseline
 398 for all stimulated contacts and sham. Across the 7 patients, compared to pre-surgical
 399 evaluation ($\text{Mdn-Baseline}_{\text{TMT-B-Time}} = 155$ s) stimulation at C0 ($\text{Mdn-C0}_{\text{TMT-B-Time}} = 77$
 400 s), C1 ($\text{Mdn-C1}_{\text{TMT-B-Time}} = 62.5$ s), and sham ($\text{Mdn-Sham}_{\text{TMT-B-Time}} = 66$ s) stimulation
 401 produced a significant decrease in TMT-B performance time ($Z=-2.366$, $P=0.018$,
 402 $r=0.894$; $Z=-1.992$, $P=0.046$, $r=0.752$; $Z=-2.366$, $P=0.018$, $r=0.894$, for C0, C1 and
 403 Sham *vs.* Baseline, respectively). Next, post-hoc Wilcoxon tests were performed on
 404 performance times at BC, C0 and Sham, relative to baseline. However, TMT-B
 405 performance time following BC ($\text{Mdn-BC}_{\text{TMT-B-Time}} = 88$ s) was not significantly
 406 different from baseline ($P = 0.866$). A Kruskal-Wallis H Test was run to test for a
 407 learning effect in TMT-A and TMT-B performance time across the 6 repetitions of the
 408 test performed during the study period. Results indicated no significant repetition effect
 409 in TMT-A ($\chi^2(5) = 2.691$, $P = 0.748$) or in TMT-B scores ($\chi^2(5) = 6.345$, $P = 0.274$).

410 **Pre-operative MRI index predicts optimal stimulation site**

411 The analysis of haemodynamic responses during symptom provocation measured with

412 fMRI was limited to the most symptomatic dimension(s) for each patient. Relative to a
413 control condition (presentation of neutral pictures), viewing predominant symptom-
414 related images produced frontal activation in all patients, of varying magnitude and
415 neuroanatomical locus (**Figure 2**). Note that different prefrontal regions are activated,
416 even when comparing patients with the same predominant symptom. For each patient,
417 probabilistic tractography was performed by placing seed regions around each of the 4
418 electrode contacts and using patient-specific frontal activations as target regions (**Figure**
419 **3**). The volume of activated tissue (VAT) for monopolar stimulation of each contact
420 was approximated as a sphere of diameter 4 mm around the contact [46]. That is,
421 connectivity between each of the contacts and that patient's fMRI activations was
422 calculated as the probability of fibers projecting from each contact VAT to the cortical
423 activated areas [44].

424 The analysis proceeded in a hierarchical manner, first examining whether our pre-
425 operative MRI index could dissociate whether the BC was in NAcc or caudate, and
426 secondly testing whether this index could determine BC identity between the two
427 contacts within-region. Thus, in a first step, we calculated for each patient, the
428 probability of fibers projecting to the activated prefrontal areas, where this projection
429 arises from a combination of VATs from NAcc contacts (C0 and C1) or caudate
430 contacts (C2 and C3). Y-BOCS reduction was also averaged for the 2 contacts in each
431 region. The clinically most effective striatal area coincided in six out of seven cases
432 with the probabilistic tractography projections from the activated prefrontal areas
433 (**Table 2**). The only patient in whom the MRI index did not coincide with maximal Y-
434 BOCS reduction is Patient 2, who is the only patient not classified as a responder to
435 DBS at any contact. Thus, limiting our sample to responder patients, all 6 from 6
436 patients' pre-operative MRI indices coincide with maximal Y-BOCS reduction
437 (Binomial test, $P = 0.031$). By contrast, the pre-operative MRI index only predicted
438 which of the two contacts within-region was most efficacious in 4 of 6 patients, which
439 was not significantly above chance levels (Binomial test, $P = 0.688$).

440 An alternative account of our findings would be that, due to individual differences in
441 anatomical connectivity and electrode localization, the notion of best contact arises
442 simply because a key area of PFC is structurally connected with the BC VAT, which
443 overlaps across patients. If this were the case, we would expect that tractographic

444 projections from the VAT of each BC would show overlap in all 6 responders. This was
445 not the case (**Figure 4A**), with maximum overlap expressed in right ventral frontal pole
446 but limited to 5 of 6 patients. Note that this analysis took C2 as BC for Patient 3; if C3
447 is taken as BC (both contacts produced equal Y-BOCS improvement in this patient) the
448 maximum overlap in prefrontal projections again observed in this ventral frontal polar
449 region but only in 4 of the 6 patients. This argues against an explanation of our findings
450 in terms of BC connectivity to a specific frontal area. Furthermore, there was even less
451 overlap across patients for predominant symptom-evoked fMRI responses, with a
452 maximum of 4 out of 6 patient overlap in several prefrontal areas (**Figure 4B**), with no
453 overlap in right ventral frontal pole.

454

455 **DISCUSSION**

456 Current debate is focused on which of the DBS targets for OCD – ALIC, VC/VS,
457 NAcc, limbic STN, or ITP – is the single most efficacious target for all possible cases of
458 OCD [7– 11]. However, the response rates to DBS to all of these targets in OCD is
459 relatively low (50%) and equivalent to that following stereotactic lesions of different
460 targets along the limbic circuit and its prefrontal projections [18,45]. By adopting an
461 alternative strategy, focusing on the symptom content of each patient, we demonstrate
462 that the optimal stimulating electrode contact location for DBS in each OCD patient is
463 not at a fixed anatomical locus within the ventral striatum or NAcc, but rather at
464 different points along the striatum. This optimal stimulation site varies between patients.
465 Symptom provocation activates specific sites of the prefrontal cortex. For example,
466 patients with contamination obsessions mainly activate the medial orbitofrontal
467 (ventromedial) cortex, while those who present checking symptoms chiefly activate the
468 dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (PFC) [15]. Tracing probabilistic tractography projections
469 from a seed defined as the volume of activated tissue of each contact towards the
470 prefrontal cortex yields a probability to hit the activated sites' volumes for each contact
471 (referred to here as the MRI index). In 6 of 7 cases, the most effective structure
472 (accumbens or caudate) was the one with the highest MRI index. Thus, stimulating at
473 this optimal contact location instead of at a fixed target increases the chance of clinical
474 response to DBS from the typical response rate of 50% [21,22], to a rate of ~86%
475 described here. It is relevant to stress that response rates in literature are quite varied. 16

476 Kohl's study stated that the average rate of responders in NAc stimulation was 45.5%
477 [21], whereas Alonso's revision [22] mentioned some successful single case studies
478 (Kuhn et al., 2007, Grant et al., 2012 and Sachdev et al, 2012), more successful trials as
479 the Denys et al., 2010 (9 out of 16) and low success studies such as Huff et al, 2010 (1
480 responder out of 10).

481 The observation that patients with different symptom content respond to specific
482 stimulation locations along a dorsoventral striatal axis raises a possibility that this
483 concept is applicable to other DBS targets. For example, the ALIC is topographically
484 organized following the same pattern as the fronto-striatal projections [46].
485 Effectiveness in other targets may, however, vary due to the fact that in these structures
486 the different subregions (*e.g.*, limbic *vs.* associative STN) are more densely packed, so it
487 is possible that several topographically distinct subregions, and their associated
488 connections, are within the same contact's volume of activated tissue. Stimulation of
489 structures that do not contribute to the patient's individual pathology could be related to
490 the appearance of reduced therapeutic effect or to side effects. For example, in OCD
491 patients treated with ALIC-DBS, stimulation of specific fiber tracts is associated with
492 Y-BOCS improvement, but the overall amount of fiber activation may be inversely
493 correlated with therapeutic effect [44].

494 We did not record any neuropsychological adverse effects after stimulation of the
495 striatum, nor recorded seizures. Although some reports warn against cognitive effects
496 from traversing or stimulating the caudate [47], others have demonstrated that the
497 striatum can be traversed without major cognitive complications [48], as was the case
498 for our patient group. Overall, the stimulation of more dorsal striatal contacts proved
499 more efficacious in our sample than the more ventral or accumbens ones. This could
500 reflect a particular skew towards more "associative" symptoms (checking, symmetry)
501 present in our patient sample than "limbic" ones (washing) Although most authors
502 claim that the most effective contacts are C0 and C1 in all patients, in some studies up
503 to 30% of patients responded best to stimulation in contacts C2 and C3 [49–51].

504 We met several methodological problems during this study. Firstly, the number of cases
505 is small, and the design is very demanding for the patients, since they had to go through
506 five different study periods, which were necessarily short (3 months) to avoid the
507 overall study being too long (already 19 months with study periods of 3 months). 17

508 During short study periods, personal events and other factors unrelated to the
509 stimulation could have strongly biased the results (in our sample, one patient had a
510 termination of pregnancy, another patient suffered the death of a brother, and a third
511 patient started a new romantic relationship during the study span). Secondly, although
512 the study was randomized and double-blind, we cannot discard a placebo effect
513 contributing to our results. Note that the Y-BOCS scores during the zero volt (sham)
514 period did not return to pre-surgical baseline values. The fact that the mean
515 improvement in contacts apart from the BC is similar to sham stimulation leads us to
516 think that BC stimulation effectively evokes clinical improvement, whereas
517 improvement during the other stimulations is due to a placebo effect or to a carry-over
518 therapeutic benefit from the previous stimulation period. Thirdly, as the Y-BOCS does
519 not distinguish in its overall score between the different symptomatic dimensions,
520 these dimensions have not been measured by the primary outcome variable.
521 Subsequently, if for example contamination/cleaning symptoms improve but
522 doubt/checking do not, the improvement in the former may not be reflected in the
523 overall Y-BOCS score. Fourthly, stimulation was bilateral, despite symptom
524 provocation fMRI often showing an asymmetric distribution of prefrontal activation.
525 Unilateral stimulation trials would have further increased the duration of the study.
526 Fifth, we used voltage setting for our electrodes, but intensity settings might have been
527 better in avoiding the effect of changes in conductivity. However, we did not observe
528 important differences in impedances tested among the contacts within each patient,
529 among the different patients, or along the different periods of the study. Lastly, the
530 MOCSS-fMRI paradigm is validated for groups of patients whereas we used this test for
531 individual patients, with 2 patients showing relatively weak activation patterns in the
532 frontal lobe.

533 By considering the “best” contact, 6 out of 7 patients with severe OCD were classified
534 as responders to DBS. The location of the best contact varied over patients, but –
535 critically – the most effective neuroanatomical target structure coincided with a pre-
536 operative MRI index derived from OCD functional MRI symptom provocation
537 combined with probabilistic tractography. We therefore show that the optimal target
538 OCD DBS is not the same for all cases, but varies in an individualized, content-specific
539 and predictable manner. These results support models of cortico-striatal loops
540 underlying the pathophysiology of OCD. Moreover, they demonstrate the efficacy of an

541 innovative therapeutic strategy, recommending a change in target-selection for
542 functional neurosurgery in psychiatric patients away from established fixed targets for
543 all cases in one disease – which only yields an average 50% response to DBS in
544 resistant OCD – to a more personalized approach based on physiological and
545 anatomical data. Since the sample studied is relatively small, this method should be
546 confirmed further with a higher number of patients, measuring DBS-evoked
547 longitudinal changes of the individual dimensions of each patient. In general, employing
548 a combination of functional imaging and tractography may represent a step towards
549 personalized functional neurosurgery.

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553 **SUPPLEMENTAL INFORMATION**

554 Supplemental Information includes 2 figures and 4 tables.

555

556

557 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS**

558 Conceptualization, JAB; Methodology, JAB, JMA-C, JAPP, BR and BAS;
559 Investigation, JAB, JMA-C, CN, RA, JG-A, BR, BAS; Writing – Original Draft, JAB,
560 CN and BAS; Writing – Review & Editing, JMA-C, RA, JG-A, JAPP and BR;
561 Funding Acquisition, JAB and BAS; Supervision, JAB, BR and BAS.

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563

564 **ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS**

565 This work was supported by the FIS PI10/01932 to JAB. BAS is supported by the
566 Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competition (Project grant SAF2015-65982-R).

567

568 **CONFLICT-OF-INTEREST POLICIES**

569

570 JAB reports having received research funding from Boston Scientific and Medtronic.

571 CN is funded by Boston Scientific. All other authors reported no biomedical financial
572 interests or potential conflicts of interest.

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769 **Figure Legends**

770 **Figure 1. Study design.** The study timeline (top) indicates the phases of the study and
 771 the duration of each phase in months. During surgery, bilateral deep brain stimulation
 772 electrodes with four contact (C0 to C3) were placed along the striatum (centre). Time 0 is
 773 defined as the beginning of the first ON trial of stimulation (**ON 1**). Each trial lasted 3
 774 months and was followed by a one month washout (**WO**) period. Note that there are 5
 775 ON trials, which pertain to the 4 electrode contacts and one sham trial. The pre-
 776 operative phase consisted of psychiatric and neuropsychological evaluation, followed
 777 by a symptom provocation study in the context of functional magnetic resonance
 778 imaging (fMRI; below left). fMRI data were analyzed to define patient-specific
 779 responses to predominant symptoms provocation (below middle). The thresholded
 780 activations were defined as termination regions during a probabilistic tractography
 781 analysis (below right), which used volume of activated tissue (VAT) around each
 782 contact as seeds. The striatum schema was taken from Haber and Knutson, 2009 [17]
 783 (Haber SN, Knutson B. The Reward Circuit: Linking Primate Anatomy and Human
 784 Imaging. *Neuropsychopharmacology* 2009;35:4–26). Permission requested.

785

786 **Figure 2. Individual patient BOLD responses during symptom provocation.** For
 787 each patient, the response to their most prominent symptom dimension (relative to
 788 baseline) is shown (masked to include only the prefrontal cortex). For patients with
 789 multiple prominent symptoms, provoked responses to each have been averaged.
 790 Statistical parametric maps are overlaid on a canonical rendering (left 3 panels) and on a
 791 midline sagittal section (right panel). All statistical parametric maps are displayed at
 792 uncorrected height threshold $P < 0.001$, unless indicated (* $P < 0.01$, ** $P < 0.005$),
 793 with cluster extent determined by AlphaSim correction at $P < 0.05$. Colorbars indicate
 794 the T -statistic of the activation. L: left, R: right.

795 **Figure 3. Probabilistic tractography from electrode contact to frontal activation.**
 796 The tracts projecting from the volume of activated tissue for 2 left-sided electrode
 797 contacts (green spheres) to the left prefrontal area activated to prevailing symptom
 798 provocation (brown) are illustrated for one example case (Patient 3) in sagittal (**A**) and
 799 3-dimensional overhead oblique transverse (**B**) section. The number of streamlines from
 800 the dorsal contact C3 (light blue) that reach the activated prefrontal area is greater than

801 the equivalent projection (red) from the ventral C0 contact in the nucleus accumbens. In
802 this patient, C3 was, together with C2, the most efficacious (or “best”) contact. Ant:
803 anterior, Post: posterior, L: left, R: right.

804 **Figure 4. Structural and functional overlap across responders ($n=6$).** (A) For each
805 patient showing a clinical response to DBS, the prefrontal termination of tracts seeded
806 from their best contact was thresholded at $P < 0.001$ and projected onto a cortical mesh.
807 The overlap of these terminations, over patients, is indicated by the color code. Note
808 that only a small region in the right frontal pole reaches an overlap of 5 patients. (B) For
809 each patient, the prefrontal response to their most prominent symptom dimension
810 (relative to baseline) was thresholded at $P < 0.05$ uncorrected and projected onto a
811 cortical mesh. Again, frequency maps were created by combining the thresholded maps
812 of the six subjects. Here, the maximum overlap was only 4 patients.

813

Personalized striatal targets for deep brain stimulation in obsessive-compulsive disorder

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Running Title

Personalized OCD striatal DBS targets

1 ABSTRACT

2

3 Background: Psychiatric conditions currently treated with deep brain stimulation
4 (DBS), such as obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD), are heterogeneous diseases with
5 different symptomatic dimensions, indicating that fixed neuroanatomical DBS targets
6 for all OCD cases may not be efficacious.

7 Objective/Hypothesis: We tested whether the optimal DBS target for OCD is fixed for
8 all patients or whether it is individualized and related to each patient's symptomatic
9 content. Further, we explored if the optimal target can be predicted by combining
10 functional neuroimaging and structural connectivity.

11 Methods: In a prospective, randomized, double-blinded study in 7 OCD patients,
12 symptomatic content was characterized pre-operatively by clinical interview and OCD
13 symptom-provocation during functional MRI. DBS electrode implantation followed a
14 trajectory placing 4 contacts along a striatal axis (nucleus accumbens to caudate).
15 Patients underwent three-month stimulation periods for each contact (and sham),
16 followed by clinical evaluation. Probabilistic tractography, applied to diffusion-
17 weighted images acquired pre-operatively, was used to study the overlap between
18 projections from the prefrontal areas activated during symptom provocation and the
19 volume of activated tissue of each electrode contact.

20 Results: Six patients were classified responders, with median symptomatic reduction
21 of 50% achieved from each patient's best contact. This was located at the caudate in 4
22 cases and at the accumbens in 2. Critically, the anatomical locus of the best contact
23 (accumbens or caudate) was related to an index derived by combining functional MRI
24 responses to prevailing symptom provocation and prefronto-cortico-striatal projections
25 defined by probabilistic tractography.

26 Conclusion: Our results therefore represent a step towards personalized, content-
27 specific DBS targets for OCD.

28

29 **Key words: deep brain stimulation, striatum, obsessive-compulsive disorder,**
30 **functional MRI, probabilistic tractography**

31 INTRODUCTION

32 Following the success of deep brain stimulation (DBS) in treating certain neurological
33 conditions such as Parkinson's disease and essential tremor, DBS is being increasingly
34 used in the management of psychiatric disorders, including treatment-resistant
35 obsessive- compulsive disorder (OCD) [1–4]. OCD is characterized by intrusive
36 distressing thoughts (obsessions) and/or repetitive mental or behavioral acts
37 (compulsions) and is a leading cause of illness- related disability [5,6]. DBS for OCD
38 has targeted regions considered components of the reward and motivation system, such
39 as the nucleus accumbens (NAcc) [7], the ventral capsule/ventral striatum VC/VS [8]
40 and the limbic portion of the subthalamic nucleus (STN) [9], as well as the anterior limb
41 of the internal capsule (ALIC) [10] and the inferior thalamic peduncle (ITP) [11]. One
42 fundamental limitation, however, is that, in contrast to neurological conditions such as
43 essential tremor where the symptomatology is relatively fixed across patients,
44 psychiatric symptoms show heterogeneity in terms of their content. In treatment-
45 resistant OCD patients undergoing DBS this is particularly relevant. OCD is a
46 heterogeneous disease in which different behaviors, or symptomatic dimensions, are
47 expressed [12]. Patients may show obsessions or compulsions of contamination and
48 washing, forbidden thoughts, doubts and checking, symmetry and ordering, repeating or
49 hoarding [13]. Seventy-four percent of patients are reported to fit into this classification
50 [14], and some patients express a combination of symptom dimensions. Despite this
51 heterogeneity, current DBS approaches target the same site across patients, regardless of
52 the content of their symptoms.

53 Determining the predominant symptoms in a given patient relies on clinical evaluation.
54 The characterization of the neural substrates of different symptomatic dimensions in
55 OCD has employed functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), applied in the
56 context of presenting patients with images corresponding to specific symptom
57 dimensions using the Maudsley Obsessive-Compulsive Stimuli Set (MOCSS) [15]. This
58 symptom provocation method reveals activations in different areas of the prefrontal
59 cortex, selectively for each symptomatic dimension. For example, patients with
60 contamination obsessions mainly activate the medial orbitofrontal (ventromedial)
61 cortex, while those who present checking symptoms chiefly activate the dorsolateral
62 prefrontal cortex (PFC) [15]. These different areas of the prefrontal cortex project to the

63 striatum into different ventrodorsally distributed areas, and not only to the NAcc or
64 ventral striatum (VS). For example, ventromedial and orbitofrontal cortex project to
65 NAcc, but dorsal anterior cingulate and dorsolateral PFC project to more dorsal portions
66 of the striatum [16–18]. Given that the pathophysiology of obsessive-compulsive
67 disorder (OCD) is thought to involve abnormal activity in fronto-striatal circuits
68 [19,20], differential engagement of PFC subdivisions during the MOCSS task as a
69 function of symptom dimension is important because it implies that different
70 subdivisions of the striatum may be differentially implicated in a given OCD patient's
71 pathophysiology. Thus, if during symptom provocation a patient exhibits increased
72 activity in dorsal frontal areas, which form part of fronto-striatal circuits involving
73 striatal regions dorsal to the NAcc, it is possible that this patient will not improve with
74 NAcc or VS stimulation simply because DBS has not targeted the pathological circuit.

75 Recent studies on DBS in OCD have shown that the overall control achieved by
76 stimulating different targets (the same single target being used in all patients within
77 each cohort) is about 50% of clinical responders [21,22]. This contrasts with patients
78 with essential tremor, in whom thalamic DBS produces postural tremor reduction in
79 89% of cases [23]. We considered that the explanation for the 50% clinical response
80 rate is the approach of treating all OCD cases with a single target, independently of their
81 symptom content. We hypothesized that the optimal striatal target for DBS in OCD
82 patients is located along the dorsoventral axis of the striatum – not limited to the NAcc
83 (or VS) – depending on the dysfunctional fronto-striatal circuit. This, in turn, would
84 depend on the particular symptom dimension of each patient, with predominant
85 symptom(s) defined as the most severe, resistant to treatment and disabling OCD
86 symptoms at the time of recruitment. To test this hypothesis, we characterized symptom
87 content-specificity of individual OCD patients using symptom-provocation fMRI prior
88 to DBS implantation. Subsequently, in a prospective double-blinded study in a series of
89 7 OCD patients that were candidates for psychiatric surgery, we tested the clinical
90 efficacy of different electrode contacts distributed along the striatum, spanning the
91 caudate and NAcc (**Figure 1**). This comprised three months of bilateral stimulation (4.5
92 V stimulation at a frequency of 130 Hz and pulse-width 60 μ s) in every electrode
93 contact (0, 1, 2, 3) and sham period (no stimulation). Furthermore, we present a novel
94 method to determine, *a priori*, which stimulation site would be optimal. Patients
95 underwent pre-operative diffusion-weighted MRI imaging (DWI) and projections

96 between prefrontal activations during symptom provocation and the 4 contact points
97 along the striatal axis were determined by applying probabilistic tractography to these
98 images. For each stimulated site, the density of prefronto-striatal projections was
99 subsequently compared with clinical efficacy of stimulation.

100

101 **METHODS**

102 *Patients*

103 Seven patients, three male aged 21-50 years; average 36.67, and four female aged 28-46
104 years; average 35.25, suffering from treatment-refractory obsessive-compulsive disorder
105 participated in this study. All patients scored 24 or higher in the Yale-Brown Obsessive-
106 Compulsive Scale (Y-BOCS) [24]. All patients provided written informed consent. The
107 study had approval from the Hospital Clínico San Carlos Ethics Committee. The study
108 is registered at clinicaltrials.gov under trial name “Deep brain Stimulation in Obsessive-
109 compulsive Disorder: Randomized, Double-blinded Clinical Trial (10/131)”,
110 registration number: NCT03217123.

111 *Patient inclusion*

112 Between June 2011 and December 2014, all patients diagnosed with OCD who attended
113 the outpatient clinic at the Psychiatry Department of Hospital Clínico San Carlos
114 (Madrid, Spain) and met study inclusion criteria were invited to participate in this study.
115 Patient demographic details are provided in **Table S1**. Inclusion criteria for functional
116 neurosurgical management were a) age 18-50 years; b) severe chronic form of
117 treatment-resistant OCD according to DSM-IV Revised criteria; c) duration of illness
118 of at least 5 years without remission; d) a Y-BOCS score $\geq 24/40$; e) treatments with
119 maximum tolerated dose of at least five serotonin reuptake inhibitors for at least 10
120 weeks, treatment with clomipramine, buspirone and lithium for at least 4 weeks, as
121 well as psychotherapy (a minimum of 20 sessions of therapist-guided exposure and
122 response prevention) simultaneously with pharmacotherapy; f) no changes in prescribed
123 medication for at least 4 weeks before; g) inability to carry out a normal social/family
124 life and impairment in daily life function; h) availability of protective and supportive
125 legal, social and familial environment for surgical treatment and rehabilitation periods;
126 i) consensus that the patient is a candidate for DBS for OCD by two independent 5

127 psychiatrists, with approval from an independent psychiatric surgery committee
128 composed of one neurosurgeon, one psychiatrist and one legal medicine expert; j)
129 ability to provide written consent for the study.

130 Exclusion criteria were: a) past or present diagnosis of psychotic disorder; b) present or
131 past substance abuse; c) any current clinically significant neurological disorder or
132 medical illness; d) any clinically significant abnormality on preoperative magnetic
133 resonance imaging; e) any DBS contraindication.

134 All patients were blind to stimulation protocol throughout the study.

135 *Psychiatric assessment*

136 Y-BOCS was the primary psychiatric variable for this study. Predominant obsessions
137 and compulsions for each patient were recorded at baseline according to standardized
138 evaluation using Y-BOCS total score. Additionally, clinical change was measured by
139 the Global Assessment of Function (GAF) score [25] and the Clinical Global
140 Impression (CGI) [26]. Thus, patients were clinically assessed with Y-BOCS, GAF and
141 CGI at baseline, at the end of every trial – three months of stimulation in every contact:
142 0, 1, 2, 3 and sham period – and after each one-month wash-out period. Standardized
143 clinical evaluation was done by a psychiatrist who was blind to stimulation protocol.
144 Pharmacological treatment did not change during the study period in all cases with the
145 exception of small variations in benzodiazepine dosage. Psychiatric scores along all
146 trials are provided in **Table S2**.

147 *Neuropsychological assessment*

148 Neuropsychological evaluation was conducted following each psychiatric assessment,
149 with evaluator blind to stimulation protocol. The main cognitive domains were
150 assessed: Free Cued Serial Recall Test [27] in abbreviated form (only 2 of the 3 test
151 trials) for learning and memory (3 different versions of the task were used across the
152 longitudinal study); Stroop Color-Word Interference Test [28] for cognitive control and
153 inhibition; phonological verbal fluency [29] and categorical verbal fluency [30] for
154 verbal fluency [31]; Letter-number sequencing from WAIS-IV for Working memory
155 [32]; Trail Making test subtest A (TMT-A) and subtest B (TMT-B) [33] for sustained
156 and divided attention, and the Wisconsin Card Sorting Test [34] for set-shifting
157 abilities, among executive functions. Neuropsychology scores at baseline, contact zero 6

158 and best contact are provided in **Table S3**.

159 *Pre-surgical Structural Neuroimaging*

160 Before surgery, structural and functional data were acquired for all patients on a 3T
161 Siemens TRIO system (Siemens, Erlangen, Germany). A standard 8 channel head coil
162 was used to acquire MPRAGE T1-weighted anatomical images with 1mm^3 resolution
163 [repetition time (TR), 2300 ms; echo time (TE), 2.98 ms; flip angle, 9°] and diffusion-
164 weighted images (DWI). DWI acquisition was based on parameters used in previous
165 probabilistic tractography studies of the basal ganglia [34]. Each volume consisted of 40
166 axial slices of 2.3mm thickness with no interslice gaps and an acquisition matrix of 96 x
167 96 in a field of view (FoV) of 220 x 100 mm, resulting in $2.3 \times 2.3 \times 2.3 \text{mm}^3$ isotropic
168 voxels [TR, 5800 ms; TE, 103 ms; flip angle, 90° ; bandwidth, 2004 Hz/pixel]. In order
169 to increase signal-to-noise, we acquired two contiguous sequences of 128 diffusion-
170 weighted images. Each dataset consisted of 64 images with diffusion gradients applied
171 along 64 non-collinear encoding directions for two different diffusion sensitization
172 strengths ($b = 500, 100\text{s/mm}^2$), and one additional image with no diffusion weighting
173 ($b = 0 \text{s/mm}^2$). A b value of zero delivers a T2-weighted EPI image for anatomical
174 reference.

175 *Pre-surgical Functional Neuroimaging*

176 fMRI data acquisition

177 For each patient, 625 gradient-echo echo-planar T2*-weighted MR image volumes with
178 blood oxygenation level-dependent (BOLD) contrast were acquired during symptom
179 provocation, plus five additional volumes, acquired at the start of each session and
180 subsequently discarded, to allow for T1 equilibration effects. Each whole-brain volume
181 comprised 40 axial slices (2.2mm thick; distance factor 0.25; TR 2.43 s; TE 30 ms; flip
182 angle 90°) sequentially acquired (ascending).

183 Symptom-provocation fMRI experiment

184 In the context of fMRI scanning, all patients performed an OCD symptom provocation
185 task. We employed a modified version of the OCD symptom-provocation paradigm
186 using the Maudsley Obsessive–Compulsive Stimuli Set (MOCSS) developed by
187 Mataix-Cols [15,35]. During scanning, patients were presented with pictures of 4
188 classes of provocative stimuli, 50 of each type: 1) contamination/washing, 2) checking, 7

189 3) hoarding, 4) symmetry/order [15,35]. Examples of washing-related pictures included
190 a public toilet, money, and a syringe. Examples of checking-related pictures included
191 electric appliances (computer, kettle, light switch), an open door, and a purse. Examples
192 of hoarding-related scenes included old newspapers/magazines, old clothes/toys, empty
193 bottles/cans, and trash bins. Examples of symmetry-related scenes included books in a
194 bookcase, a CD rack and a bathroom cabinet. In addition, 50 pictures of neutral scenes
195 (e.g., furniture, nature scenes household items) were selected from a standard set of
196 stimuli [36]. These stimuli had previously been carefully chosen [35] to avoid
197 resembling common triggers of OCD symptoms. Note that 11 pictures of the MOCSS,
198 pertaining to UK electrical plugs/sockets, money, cash-point and written English, were
199 substituted for equivalent Spanish pictures obtained with a standard digital camera
200 (Sony NEX-VG10E).

201 The study comprised 4 ‘blocks’ pertaining to the 4 classes of provocative stimuli. Each
202 block consisted of ten 20s alternating epochs in which subjects viewed either 10
203 provocative or 10 neutral pictures. Each picture was presented for 1950 ms (inter-
204 stimulus interval 50 ms). Each epoch began with an 8 s period during which patients
205 were played a prerecorded voice via MR-compatible headphones (VisuaStim XGA;
206 Resonance Technology, Northridge, CA), instructing them to imagine being in a
207 particular situation while looking at the scenes they were about to see (there were five
208 slightly different recordings per type of stimuli in each experiment, to avoid monotony).
209 We presented the same instructions as used previously [15], but recorded in Spanish.
210 Some examples of these instructions are the following: For washing-related pictures:
211 “Imagine that you must come into contact with what’s shown in the following pictures
212 without washing yourself afterward.” For checking-related pictures: “Imagine that you
213 are not sure whether you switched off or locked the following objects and it is
214 impossible for you to go back and check.” For hoarding-related pictures: “Imagine that
215 the following objects belong to you and that you must throw them away forever.” For
216 symmetry-related pictures: “Imagine that you are not allowed to put the following items
217 in order.” For neutral scenes: “Imagine that you are completely relaxed while looking at
218 the following scenes.” After each set of pictures, another prerecorded sound file of the
219 question “How anxious do you feel?” was played. Patients had to rate their subjective
220 anxiety by pushing one of 5 buttons to indicate from 0 (no anxiety) to 4 (extreme
221 anxiety).

222 *Neurosurgical procedure*

223 The day before the operation, a volumetric CT scan (Philips ® Brilliance 64 CT
224 Scanner) was performed and fused with a contrast-enhanced T1 MRI and T2 volumetric
225 images. The location of the posterior border of the anterior commissure (AC) and the
226 anterior border of the posterior commissure (PC) were marked, and the target
227 determined by measuring the distances from the AC-PC line and the mid-sagittal plane,
228 using a Medtronic Stealth Station Treon navigation system (Medtronic Minneapolis,
229 USA). The target for the NAcc was placed at the coordinates reported by [7]: 2.5 mm
230 rostral to the anterior border of the anterior commissure, 4.5 mm ventral to the AC-PC
231 line, and 6.5 mm lateral to the mid- sagittal plane. A trajectory was planned to reach the
232 target point at the NAcc close to the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis (distal electrode
233 or contact “0”), and for placing the rest of the contacts of a Medtronic Model 3391
234 stimulating macroelectrode at several points along the striatum avoiding the ventricles
235 (contacts 1, 2, and 3; **Figure 1 and Figure S1**).

236 On the operative day, a burr hole was performed on each side, the dura opened and the
237 hole sealed with DuraSeal (DuraSeal Dural Sealant System, Confluent Surgical, Inc.,
238 Waltham, Massachusetts) to avoid CSF reflux. A microelectrode FC 4000 (FHC,
239 Bowdoin, Maine, USA) was advanced into the ventral striatum towards the target using
240 a Microdrive (Elekta MicroDrive™). In the case of relatively silent neuronal activity,
241 the target was advanced 2 mm anteriorly. After microelectrode recording, the
242 macroelectrode was implanted at the determined target, and the clinical effects were
243 tested using an external tester (Medtronic Model 3625 Test Stimulator). Bipolar
244 stimulation at 3.5 V between the most distal and the most proximal contacts (negative
245 polarity most distal) was delivered at 130 Hz (pulse width 60 µs), and then increased up
246 to 5 V to screen for undesired side effects (none of which appeared in any case). Intra-
247 operative X-ray was used to verify the positioning of the two electrodes. Post-operative
248 CT verified final electrode position.

249 After implantation, the lead extensions were externalized and all possible combinations
250 of the electrode leads were tested for their effectiveness using an external tester. After
251 the external stimulation trial period, an Activa PC Model 37601 neurostimulator
252 (Medtronic Inc) was implanted subcutaneously at the abdominal left flank and
253 connected to the electrodes using an extension cable 33086 (Medtronic Inc).

254 *Deep brain Stimulation Protocol*

255 After surgery, a simple randomized sequence of contact activations (C0, 1, 2, 3) and
256 sham (-), was generated for each patient. Each contact was stimulated at 130 Hz, pulse-
257 width 60 μ s, and 4.5 V for three months (the sham activation was 0 V) according to the
258 patient's individual sequence, separated by one month of washout with the generator
259 turned off (**Figure 1**). The study meets a double-blind, longitudinal design. Stimulation
260 contact was set following a random series known only by the neurosurgeon, whereas
261 patient, psychiatry and neuropsychology teams were blinded. Some patients referred a
262 transient sense of wellbeing when contact 0 was stimulated for the first time during
263 stimulation trials prior to, but not during, the longitudinal study.

264 **Statistical analysis**

265 *Statistical Analysis of Psychiatric and Neuropsychological Data*

266 Psychiatric and neuropsychological scale results in the multiple stimulation periods
267 were analyzed with repeated measures non-parametric Friedman test. To evaluate
268 pairwise significant differences between the pre-surgery scores, C0 score, and BC
269 scores, non-parametric Wilcoxon's test was used. All statistical analyses were
270 performed using IBM SPSS Statistics software version 20, and results considered
271 significant at alpha level 0.05. Statistical parameters can be found in the Results section.

272 *Neuroimaging analysis*

273 **fMRI Data Analysis**

274 Functional imaging data were analyzed using statistical parametric mapping (SPM12;
275 <http://www.fil.ion.ucl.ac.uk/spm>) employing an epoch-related model. Each imaging
276 time series was realigned to correct for interscan movement, slice-time corrected,
277 normalized into a standard anatomical space, and smoothed with a Gaussian kernel of
278 8mm full width half-maximum. To test for symptom-provocation effects, we specified
279 four effects of interest: the epochs corresponding to each symptom dimension. Epoch-
280 specific responses were modeled by convolving a box-car function spanning epoch
281 duration with a canonical hemodynamic response function (HRF) to create regressors of
282 interest. Events corresponding to viewing instructions, and questions regarding anxiety
283 levels, were modeled as separate regressors. Six movement parameters were modeled as
284 nuisance covariates.

285 The predominant symptom(s) for each patient was defined (**Table 1**) and used to
286 construct a contrast of responses to provocation relative to the neutral pictures baseline.
287 The ensuing statistical parametric map for this contrast was thresholded at $P < 0.001$
288 uncorrected (unless otherwise stated). Note that due to weak responses during symptom
289 activation in patients 4 and 6, the SPMs for these patients were first thresholded at $P <$
290 0.01 and 0.005 uncorrected, respectively. AlphaSim was used to correct for multiple
291 comparisons at the cluster level ($P < 0.05$) for each patient. Alphasim thresholding was
292 performed for the number of comparisons defined within a prefrontal mask accounting
293 for the applied smoothing, (FWHM 8mm). Different cluster thresholds (K) were
294 obtained for the three pre-defined statistical thresholds: $P < 0.01$ $K > 86$; $P < 0.005$ $K > 58$;
295 $P < 0.001$ $K > 26$. The prefrontal mask was created by combining the following regions
296 from the Harvard-Oxford cortical atlas distributed with FSL
297 (<https://fsl.fmrib.ox.ac.uk/fsl/fslwiki>): Superior Frontal Gyrus, Middle Frontal Gyrus,
298 Inferior Frontal Gyrus pars triangularis and pars opercularis, Frontal Orbital Cortex,
299 Supplementary motor cortex, Paracingulate Gyrus, Frontal Pole, Cingulate Gyrus
300 (Anterior Division), Subcallosal Cortex, Frontal Operculum Cortex, and Frontal Medial
301 Cortex.

302 Probabilistic Tractography Analysis

303 In a first step, each patient's electrode contacts were localized as follows. We extracted
304 subject-specific volumetric masks of the caudate and accumbens nucleus in both
305 hemispheres using an automated sub-cortical segmentation procedure in Freesurfer
306 V5.1.0 [36]. Affine linear transformations between different image spaces were
307 performed using FSL FLIRT [37]. Non-brain tissues were removed from T1-weighted
308 images using FSL BET [38]. Post-operative CT images were thresholded to segment the
309 skull and remove it from the unthresholded image and co-registered to the pre-operative
310 T1-weighted image. The post-operative CT was again thresholded at an intensity of
311 1500 to retain just the electrodes in the T1-weighted image space. The contacts'
312 coordinates were identified visually after superimposing the post-operative CT on the
313 pre-operative T1-weighted MRI (**Figure S1**). A spherical region with a radius of 4mm
314 was then created at each contact coordinate.

315 Diffusion weighted imaging data were pre-processed using FSL BET [38] for non-brain
316 tissue removal and FSL FDT for eddy currents correction [39]. Estimation of the 11

317 diffusion parameters was performed using BEDPOSTX [40]. We used a multi-shell
318 model for the fitting of the parameters [41]. White matter connectivity was quantified
319 using probabilistic tractography with FDT Protrackx 2.0 [42]. The contact spherical
320 regions were used as seeds for the tractography analysis, and the fMRI activations were
321 used as waypoints and termination masks. The rest of the parameters for the
322 tractography analyses were kept as default, *i.e.*, 5000 streamlines per voxel, a maximum
323 length of 2000 steps, minimum step length of 0.5mm, and a curvature threshold of 80°.
324 That is, we applied the default settings in FSL, standard in the field, in our tractography
325 analyses.

326 For display of structural and functional overlap, tractographic terminations or fMRI
327 activations were projected onto a cortical mesh using CARET (Computerized
328 Anatomical Reconstruction Toolkit) software[43].

329 Pre-operative MRI index calculation

330 For a given electrode contact, or group of contacts, the MRI index, denoted as $p(\text{tracts})$,
331 is the probability (%) of reaching the fMRI activation by seeding streamlines at the
332 volume of activated tissues (VATs) of the electrode contact(s).

333

334 **RESULTS**

335 **The most effective striatal stimulation site varies between patients**

336 Electrodes were successfully placed along a striatal axis in all patients, with two
337 contacts in NAcc (C0, C1) and two in the caudate head (C2, C3), bilaterally. This is
338 evident on inspecting the fusion of each patient's post-operative computed tomography
339 (CT) scan with the pre-operative structural MRI (**Figure S1**). Across the 7 patients, the
340 main obsession(s) and compulsion(s) showed heterogeneity (**Table 1**). For each patient,
341 the contact yielding lowest Y-BOCS score achieved during the longitudinal study was
342 labeled as "best" contact (BC). The neuroanatomical locus of the BC varied between
343 patients (**Table 1, Table S2**) and was more frequently observed in caudate than
344 accumbens nucleus (**Table S3, Figure S2**). According to current convention [45],
345 patients with a Y-BOCS score decrease of more than 35% with respect to baseline are
346 considered DBS responders. Of the seven patients studied, clinical improvement
347 following BC stimulation exceeded 35% in six patients (**Table 1**), with a median (Mdn) 12

348 Y-BOCS reduction of 47.37% at their BC. Directly contrasting this finding against
 349 clinical efficacy of the commonly stimulated most distal contact (C0) in the NAcc, we
 350 observe that across the group, stimulation of C0 achieved a Mdn Y-BOCS reduction of
 351 21.62% (**Table S3**). Only two participants (28.57%) would have been classified as
 352 responders if C0 alone had been stimulated, and in both cases (Patients 1 and 3), the BC
 353 was not in contact 0 (**Table 1**), *i.e.*, stimulation at more dorsal striatal sites were more
 354 effective in these patients.

355 Differential clinical response as a function of stimulated contact was confirmed by a
 356 Friedman Test on Y-BOCS scores for all stimulation trials, baseline and sham across
 357 the 7 patients ($\chi^2(5)=17.941$, $P=0.003$, Kendall $W=0.513$). Post-hoc Wilcoxon signed-
 358 rank tests were first performed to test for improvement relative to pre-surgical baseline
 359 for all stimulated contacts and sham. Across the 7 patients, compared to pre-surgical
 360 evaluation (Mdn- Baseline_{Y-BOCS} = 32), stimulation at C0 (Mdn-C0_{Y-BOCS} = 24), C1
 361 (Mdn-C1_{Y-BOCS} = 22), C2 (Mdn-C2_{Y-BOCS} = 17), C3 (Mdn-C3_{Y-BOCS} = 22) and sham
 362 (Mdn-Sham_{Y-BOCS} = 20) stimulation all produced a significant decrease in Y-BOCS
 363 scores ($Z=-2.120$, $P=0.034$, effect size $r=0.801$; $Z=-2.371$, $P=0.018$, $r=0.896$; $Z=-$
 364 2.371 , $P=0.018$, $r=0.896$; $Z=-2.375$, $P=0.018$, $r=0.897$; $Z=-2.366$, $P=0.018$, $r=0.894$
 365 for C0, C1, C2, C3 and Sham *vs.* Baseline, respectively). Next, post-hoc Wilcoxon tests
 366 were performed on percent improvement in Y-BOCS score at BC, contact Zero and
 367 Sham (each relative to baseline). Specifically confirming our hypothesis that BC
 368 outperforms NAcc C0 stimulation, the percentage Y-BOCS score improvement was
 369 significantly greater at BC (Mdn-BC_{Y-BOCS} decrease = 47.37%) than at C0 (Mdn-C0_{Y-}
 370 _{BOCS} decrease = 21.62%) ($Z=-2.207$, $P=0.027$, $r=0.834$). **There was a trend in Y-BOCS**
 371 **improvement at BC relative to sham stimulation (Mdn-Sham_{Y-BOCS} = 25.00%) ($Z=-$**
 372 **1.859**, $P=0.063$, $r=0.702$), stimulation at C0 yielded actually marginally less Y-BOCS
 373 improvement than during Sham ($Z=-1.782$, $P=0.075$, $r=0.673$). We note, however, that
 374 Patient 3 underwent a major life event during her Sham period (discussed below).
 375 Repeating the Wilcoxon test excluding this patient shows a significant improvement of
 376 BC over Sham stimulation ($Z=-1.992$, $P=0.046$, $r=0.752$) and no Y-BOCS improvement
 377 difference between C0 and Sham stimulation ($Z=-1.483$, $P=0.138$).

378 We note that in Patients 3 and 7, it is quite probable that the most distal electrode
 379 contact is placed at the ventricles (**Figure S1**). In neither case was this contact (C0) the

380 most effective contact. Y-BOCS reduction following stimulation this distal contact was
 381 either at the same level (Patient 7) or less than (Patient 3) that observed during sham
 382 stimulation.

383 In addition to our primary outcome measure (Y-BOCS), anxiety measures were
 384 collected using the STAI state scale and Hamilton anxiety rating scale (HAM-A) at all
 385 evaluation periods in Patients 4 to 7. A Friedman Test on these scores for all stimulation
 386 trials, baseline and sham across the 4 patients showed a significant effect for HAM-A
 387 ($\chi^2(5)=11.143$, $P=0.049$). **Additionally, there was a trend in STAI-state improvement**
 388 **($\chi^2(5)=10.857$, $P=0.054$) under the best contact relative to the rest of the trials.** For both
 389 scores, post-hoc Wilcoxon tests comparing each stimulation period with baseline, or BC
 390 with baseline, did not reveal any significant effects.

391 **Striatal stimulation has limited effects on cognitive function**

392 DBS at different striatal sites produced limited effects on cognitive testing. For each
 393 neuropsychological test (**Table S4**), scores as a function of stimulated contact were
 394 entered into a Friedman Test for all stimulation trials, baseline and sham across the 7
 395 patients. Statistically significant effects were only observed for Trail Making Test-B
 396 (TMT-B) performance times ($\chi^2(5)=13.787$, $P=0.017$, Kendall $W=0.460$). Post-hoc
 397 Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were performed on scores relative to pre-surgical baseline
 398 for all stimulated contacts and sham. Across the 7 patients, compared to pre-surgical
 399 evaluation ($\text{Mdn-Baseline}_{\text{TMT-B-Time}} = 155$ s) stimulation at C0 ($\text{Mdn-C0}_{\text{TMT-B-Time}} = 77$
 400 s), C1 ($\text{Mdn-C1}_{\text{TMT-B-Time}} = 62.5$ s), and sham ($\text{Mdn-Sham}_{\text{TMT-B-Time}} = 66$ s) stimulation
 401 produced a significant decrease in TMT-B performance time ($Z=-2.366$, $P=0.018$,
 402 $r=0.894$; $Z=-1.992$, $P=0.046$, $r=0.752$; $Z=-2.366$, $P=0.018$, $r=0.894$, for C0, C1 and
 403 Sham *vs.* Baseline, respectively). Next, post-hoc Wilcoxon tests were performed on
 404 performance times at BC, C0 and Sham, relative to baseline. However, TMT-B
 405 performance time following BC ($\text{Mdn-BC}_{\text{TMT-B-Time}} = 88$ s) was not significantly
 406 different from baseline ($P = 0.866$). A Kruskal-Wallis H Test was run to test for a
 407 learning effect in TMT-A and TMT-B performance time across the 6 repetitions of the
 408 test performed during the study period. Results indicated no significant repetition effect
 409 in TMT-A ($\chi^2(5) = 2.691$, $P = 0.748$) or in TMT-B scores ($\chi^2(5) = 6.345$, $P = 0.274$).

410 **Pre-operative MRI index predicts optimal stimulation site**

411 The analysis of haemodynamic responses during symptom provocation measured with

412 fMRI was limited to the most symptomatic dimension(s) for each patient. Relative to a
413 control condition (presentation of neutral pictures), viewing predominant symptom-
414 related images produced frontal activation in all patients, of varying magnitude and
415 neuroanatomical locus (**Figure 2**). Note that different prefrontal regions are activated,
416 even when comparing patients with the same predominant symptom. For each patient,
417 probabilistic tractography was performed by placing seed regions around each of the 4
418 electrode contacts and using patient-specific frontal activations as target regions (**Figure**
419 **3**). The volume of activated tissue (VAT) for monopolar stimulation of each contact
420 was approximated as a sphere of diameter 4 mm around the contact [46]. That is,
421 connectivity between each of the contacts and that patient's fMRI activations was
422 calculated as the probability of fibers projecting from each contact VAT to the cortical
423 activated areas [44].

424 The analysis proceeded in a hierarchical manner, first examining whether our pre-
425 operative MRI index could dissociate whether the BC was in NAcc or caudate, and
426 secondly testing whether this index could determine BC identity between the two
427 contacts within-region. Thus, in a first step, we calculated for each patient, the
428 probability of fibers projecting to the activated prefrontal areas, where this projection
429 arises from a combination of VATs from NAcc contacts (C0 and C1) or caudate
430 contacts (C2 and C3). Y-BOCS reduction was also averaged for the 2 contacts in each
431 region. The clinically most effective striatal area coincided in six out of seven cases
432 with the probabilistic tractography projections from the activated prefrontal areas
433 (**Table 2**). The only patient in whom the MRI index did not coincide with maximal Y-
434 BOCS reduction is Patient 2, who is the only patient not classified as a responder to
435 DBS at any contact. Thus, limiting our sample to responder patients, all 6 from 6
436 patients' pre-operative MRI indices coincide with maximal Y-BOCS reduction
437 (Binomial test, $P = 0.031$). By contrast, the pre-operative MRI index only predicted
438 which of the two contacts within-region was most efficacious in 4 of 6 patients, which
439 was not significantly above chance levels (Binomial test, $P = 0.688$).

440 An alternative account of our findings would be that, due to individual differences in
441 anatomical connectivity and electrode localization, the notion of best contact arises
442 simply because a key area of PFC is structurally connected with the BC VAT, which
443 overlaps across patients. If this were the case, we would expect that tractographic

444 projections from the VAT of each BC would show overlap in all 6 responders. This was
445 not the case (**Figure 4A**), with maximum overlap expressed in right ventral frontal pole
446 but limited to 5 of 6 patients. Note that this analysis took C2 as BC for Patient 3; if C3
447 is taken as BC (both contacts produced equal Y-BOCS improvement in this patient) the
448 maximum overlap in prefrontal projections again observed in this ventral frontal polar
449 region but only in 4 of the 6 patients. This argues against an explanation of our findings
450 in terms of BC connectivity to a specific frontal area. Furthermore, there was even less
451 overlap across patients for predominant symptom-evoked fMRI responses, with a
452 maximum of 4 out of 6 patient overlap in several prefrontal areas (**Figure 4B**), with no
453 overlap in right ventral frontal pole.

454

455 **DISCUSSION**

456 Current debate is focused on which of the DBS targets for OCD – ALIC, VC/VS,
457 NAcc, limbic STN, or ITP – is the single most efficacious target for all possible cases of
458 OCD [7– 11]. However, the response rates to DBS to all of these targets in OCD is
459 relatively low (50%) and equivalent to that following stereotactic lesions of different
460 targets along the limbic circuit and its prefrontal projections [18,45]. By adopting an
461 alternative strategy, focusing on the symptom content of each patient, we demonstrate
462 that the optimal stimulating electrode contact location for DBS in each OCD patient is
463 not at a fixed anatomical locus within the ventral striatum or NAcc, but rather at
464 different points along the striatum. This optimal stimulation site varies between patients.
465 Symptom provocation activates specific sites of the prefrontal cortex. For example,
466 patients with contamination obsessions mainly activate the medial orbitofrontal
467 (ventromedial) cortex, while those who present checking symptoms chiefly activate the
468 dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (PFC) [15]. Tracing probabilistic tractography projections
469 from a seed defined as the volume of activated tissue of each contact towards the
470 prefrontal cortex yields a probability to hit the activated sites' volumes for each contact
471 (referred to here as the MRI index). In 6 of 7 cases, the most effective structure
472 (accumbens or caudate) was the one with the highest MRI index. Thus, stimulating at
473 this optimal contact location instead of at a fixed target increases the chance of clinical
474 response to DBS from the typical response rate of 50% [21,22], to a rate of ~86%
475 described here. It is relevant to stress that response rates in literature are quite varied. 16

476 Kohl's study stated that the average rate of responders in NAc stimulation was 45.5%
477 [21], whereas Alonso's revision [22] mentioned some successful single case studies
478 (Kuhn et al., 2007, Grant et al., 2012 and Sachdev et al, 2012), more successful trials as
479 the Denys et al., 2010 (9 out of 16) and low success studies such as Huff et al, 2010 (1
480 responder out of 10).

481 The observation that patients with different symptom content respond to specific
482 stimulation locations along a dorsoventral striatal axis raises a possibility that this
483 concept is applicable to other DBS targets. For example, the ALIC is topographically
484 organized following the same pattern as the fronto-striatal projections [46].
485 Effectiveness in other targets may, however, vary due to the fact that in these structures
486 the different subregions (*e.g.*, limbic *vs.* associative STN) are more densely packed, so it
487 is possible that several topographically distinct subregions, and their associated
488 connections, are within the same contact's volume of activated tissue. Stimulation of
489 structures that do not contribute to the patient's individual pathology could be related to
490 the appearance of reduced therapeutic effect or to side effects. For example, in OCD
491 patients treated with ALIC-DBS, stimulation of specific fiber tracts is associated with
492 Y-BOCS improvement, but the overall amount of fiber activation may be inversely
493 correlated with therapeutic effect [44].

494 We did not record any neuropsychological adverse effects after stimulation of the
495 striatum, nor recorded seizures. Although some reports warn against cognitive effects
496 from traversing or stimulating the caudate [47], others have demonstrated that the
497 striatum can be traversed without major cognitive complications [48], as was the case
498 for our patient group. Overall, the stimulation of more dorsal striatal contacts proved
499 more efficacious in our sample than the more ventral or accumbens ones. This could
500 reflect a particular skew towards more "associative" symptoms (checking, symmetry)
501 present in our patient sample than "limbic" ones (washing) Although most authors
502 claim that the most effective contacts are C0 and C1 in all patients, in some studies up
503 to 30% of patients responded best to stimulation in contacts C2 and C3 [49–51].

504 We met several methodological problems during this study. Firstly, the number of cases
505 is small, and the design is very demanding for the patients, since they had to go through
506 five different study periods, which were necessarily short (3 months) to avoid the
507 overall study being too long (already 19 months with study periods of 3 months). 17

508 During short study periods, personal events and other factors unrelated to the
509 stimulation could have strongly biased the results (in our sample, one patient had a
510 termination of pregnancy, another patient suffered the death of a brother, and a third
511 patient started a new romantic relationship during the study span). Secondly, although
512 the study was randomized and double-blind, we cannot discard a placebo effect
513 contributing to our results. Note that the Y-BOCS scores during the zero volt (sham)
514 period did not return to pre-surgical baseline values. The fact that the mean
515 improvement in contacts apart from the BC is similar to sham stimulation leads us to
516 think that BC stimulation **effectively** evokes clinical improvement, whereas
517 improvement during the other stimulations is due to a placebo effect or to a carry-over
518 therapeutic benefit from the previous stimulation period. Thirdly, as the Y-BOCS does
519 not distinguish in its overall score between the different symptomatic dimensions,
520 these dimensions have not been measured by the primary outcome variable.
521 Subsequently, if for example contamination/cleaning symptoms improve but
522 doubt/checking do not, the improvement in the former may not be reflected in the
523 overall Y-BOCS score. Fourthly, stimulation was bilateral, despite symptom
524 provocation fMRI often showing an asymmetric distribution of prefrontal activation.
525 Unilateral stimulation trials would have further increased the duration of the study.
526 Fifth, we used voltage setting for our electrodes, but intensity settings might have been
527 better in avoiding the effect of changes in conductivity. However, we did not observe
528 important differences in impedances tested among the contacts within each patient,
529 among the different patients, or along the different periods of the study. Lastly, the
530 MOCSS-fMRI paradigm is validated for groups of patients whereas we used this test for
531 individual patients, with 2 patients showing relatively weak activation patterns in the
532 frontal lobe.

533 By considering the “best” contact, 6 out of 7 patients with severe OCD were classified
534 as responders to DBS. The location of the best contact varied over patients, but –
535 critically – the most effective neuroanatomical target structure coincided with a pre-
536 operative MRI index derived from OCD functional MRI symptom provocation
537 combined with probabilistic tractography. We therefore show that the optimal target
538 OCD DBS is not the same for all cases, but varies in an individualized, content-specific
539 and predictable manner. These results support models of cortico-striatal loops
540 underlying the pathophysiology of OCD. Moreover, they demonstrate the efficacy of an

541 innovative therapeutic strategy, recommending a change in target-selection for
542 functional neurosurgery in psychiatric patients away from established fixed targets for
543 all cases in one disease – which only yields an average 50% response to DBS in
544 resistant OCD – to a more personalized approach based on physiological and
545 anatomical data. Since the sample studied is relatively small, this method should be
546 confirmed further with a higher number of patients, measuring DBS-evoked
547 longitudinal changes of the individual dimensions of each patient. In general, employing
548 a combination of functional imaging and tractography may represent a step towards
549 personalized functional neurosurgery.

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553 **SUPPLEMENTAL INFORMATION**

554 Supplemental Information includes 2 figures and 4 tables.

555

556

557 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS**

558 Conceptualization, JAB; Methodology, JAB, JMA-C, JAPP, BR and BAS;
559 Investigation, JAB, JMA-C, CN, RA, JG-A, BR, BAS; Writing – Original Draft, JAB,
560 CN and BAS; Writing – Review & Editing, JMA-C, RA, JG-A, JAPP and BR;
561 Funding Acquisition, JAB and BAS; Supervision, JAB, BR and BAS.

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563

564 **ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS**

565 This work was supported by the FIS PI10/01932 to JAB. BAS is supported by the
566 Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competition (Project grant SAF2015-65982-R).

567

568 **CONFLICT-OF-INTEREST POLICIES**

569

570 JAB reports having received research funding from Boston Scientific and Medtronic.

571 CN is funded by Boston Scientific. All other authors reported no biomedical financial
572 interests or potential conflicts of interest.

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769 **Figure Legends**

770 **Figure 1. Study design.** The study timeline (top) indicates the phases of the study and
 771 the duration of each phase in months. During surgery, bilateral deep brain stimulation
 772 electrodes with four contact (C0 to C3) were placed along the striatum (centre). Time 0 is
 773 defined as the beginning of the first ON trial of stimulation (**ON 1**). Each trial lasted 3
 774 months and was followed by a one month washout (**WO**) period. Note that there are 5
 775 ON trials, which pertain to the 4 electrode contacts and one sham trial. The pre-
 776 operative phase consisted of psychiatric and neuropsychological evaluation, followed
 777 by a symptom provocation study in the context of functional magnetic resonance
 778 imaging (fMRI; below left). fMRI data were analyzed to define patient-specific
 779 responses to predominant symptoms provocation (below middle). The thresholded
 780 activations were defined as termination regions during a probabilistic tractography
 781 analysis (below right), which used volume of activated tissue (VAT) around each
 782 contact as seeds. The striatum schema was taken from Haber and Knutson, 2009 [17]
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786 **Figure 2. Individual patient BOLD responses during symptom provocation.** For
 787 each patient, the response to their most prominent symptom dimension (relative to
 788 baseline) is shown (masked to include only the prefrontal cortex). For patients with
 789 multiple prominent symptoms, provoked responses to each have been averaged.
 790 Statistical parametric maps are overlaid on a canonical rendering (left 3 panels) and on a
 791 midline sagittal section (right panel). All statistical parametric maps are displayed at
 792 uncorrected height threshold $P < 0.001$, unless indicated (* $P < 0.01$, ** $P < 0.005$),
 793 with cluster extent determined by AlphaSim correction at $P < 0.05$. Colorbars indicate
 794 the T -statistic of the activation. L: left, R: right.

795 **Figure 3. Probabilistic tractography from electrode contact to frontal activation.**

796 The tracts projecting from the volume of activated tissue for 2 left-sided electrode
 797 contacts (green spheres) to the left prefrontal area activated to prevailing symptom
 798 provocation (brown) are illustrated for one example case (Patient 3) in sagittal (**A**) and
 799 3-dimensional overhead oblique transverse (**B**) section. The number of streamlines from
 800 the dorsal contact C3 (light blue) that reach the activated prefrontal area is greater than

801 the equivalent projection (red) from the ventral C0 contact in the nucleus accumbens. In
802 this patient, C3 was, together with C2, the most efficacious (or “best”) contact. Ant:
803 anterior, Post: posterior, L: left, R: right.

804 **Figure 4. Structural and functional overlap across responders ($n=6$).** (A) For each
805 patient showing a clinical response to DBS, the prefrontal termination of tracts seeded
806 from their best contact was thresholded at $P < 0.001$ and projected onto a cortical mesh.
807 The overlap of these terminations, over patients, is indicated by the color code. Note
808 that only a small region in the right frontal pole reaches an overlap of 5 patients. (B) For
809 each patient, the prefrontal response to their most prominent symptom dimension
810 (relative to baseline) was thresholded at $P < 0.05$ uncorrected and projected onto a
811 cortical mesh. Again, frequency maps were created by combining the thresholded maps
812 of the six subjects. Here, the maximum overlap was only 4 patients.

813

Contacts' VATs defined as Tractography seed regions

A [Click here to download Figure: Figure3_ Revised.pdf](#)

B

A Overlap of prefrontal cortical projections from BC

[Click here to download Figure: Figure4_Revised.pdf](#)

B Overlap of fMRI responses during predominant symptom provocation

Patient 1 Checking

Patient 2 Checking & Symmetry

Patient 3 Checking & Washing

Patient 4 Checking*

Patient 5 Checking

Patient 6 Washing**

Patient 7 Washing

R hemisphere

L hemisphere

Pt	Main Obsessions	Main Compulsions	Other OCD Symptoms	Best contact	Y-BOCS pre	Y-BOCS C0	Y-BOCS Best	% C0	% Best
1	Doubts	Checking		2	36	19	1	47.22	97.22
2	Symmetry, Doubts	Ordering, Checking	Contamination/ Cleaning	0,2	32	24	24	25.00	25.00
3	Contamination, Doubts	Cleaning Checking		2,3	29	17	16	41.38	44.83
4	Doubts, aggressive obsessive thoughts	Checking		2	24	23	11	4.17	54.17
5	Doubts	Checking	Contamination/ Cleaning	3	38	32	20	15.79	47.37
6	Contamination	Cleaning	Symmetry/ Ordering, Taboo thoughts, Hoarding	1	30	31	19	-3.33	36.67
7	Contamination	Cleaning	Doubts/ Checking	2	37	29	17	21.62	54.05
Median Y-BOCS improvement across patients								21.62	47.37
Mean Y-BOCS improvement across patients								21.69	51.33
Percentage of responders (patients showing at least 35% reduction in Y-BOCS score)								28.57	85.71

Table 1: Patient symptomatology and DBS effects within the study sample. “Main Obsessions” and “Main Compulsions” are defined as the most severe, resistant to treatment and disabling OCD symptoms at the time of recruitment for each patient (Pt). “Other OCD symptoms” are defined as concomitant OCD obsessions and compulsions with less degree of severity, resistance to treatment and disability. “Best contact” indicates the stimulation contact (0, 1, 2 or 3) along the electrode that yielded the lowest Y-BOCS score. “Y-BOCS pre”, “Y-BOCS C0” and “Y-BOCS Best” pertain to the Y-BOCS score at baseline, following stimulation of contact 0, and following stimulation of the best contact, respectively. “% C0” and “% Best” pertain to the percentage of Y-BOCS score improvement with respect to baseline following stimulation of contact 0, and following stimulation of the best contact, respectively.

Pt	NAcc (contacts C0,C1)		Caudate (contacts C2,C3)		Contact	Does best %Y-BOCS ↓ coincide with higher p(tracts)?	Ventral contact		Dorsal contact		Does best %Y-BOCS ↓ coincide with higher p(tracts)?
	p(tracts)	% Y-BOCS ↓	p(tracts)	% Y-BOCS ↓	BC		p(tracts)	% Y-BOCS ↓	p(tracts)	% Y-BOCS ↓	
1	0.014	43.06	4.761	68.06	2	Yes - in Caudate	C2 0.008	C2 97.22	C3 9.514	C3 38.89	Yes – C3
2	3.200	17.19	16.762	15.63	0, 2	No					
3	1.973	36.21	4.812	44.83	2, 3	Yes - in Caudate	C2 4.795	C2 44.83	C3 4.830	C3 44.83	Yes – C2/C3
4	0.016	16.67	0.039	29.17	2	Yes - in Caudate	C2 0.012	C2 54.17	C3 0.067	C3 4.17	No
5	6.619	30.26	3.661	25.00	3	Yes - in NAcc	C0 1.912	C0 15.79	C1 11.327	C1 44.74	Yes – C1
6	0.117	16.67	0.067	8.33	1	Yes - in NAcc	C0 0.198	C0 -3.33	C1 0.037	C1 36.67	No
7	0.008	28.38	0.058	51.35	2	Yes - in Caudate	C2 0.027	C2 54.05	C3 0.088	C3 48.65	Yes – C3

Table 2. Pre-operative structural-functional MRI index determines in which neuroanatomical locus DBS will lead to most reduction in Y-BOCS. Pt: Patient. p(tracts): probability (%) of reaching the fMRI activation by seeding streamlines at the volume of activated tissues (VATs) of each specific electrode contact. % Y-BOCS ↓: percent reduction in Y-BOCS score following stimulation of a structure (NAcc or Caudate, expressed as average Y-BOCS reduction following stimulation of C0 and C1 or C2 and C3, respectively) or following stimulation of individual contacts within a structure (ventral or dorsal contacts).

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Revised_Supplementary Item

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Revised_Supplementary Figure 1

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Supplementary Figure 2

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